

Information Overload and the Acceptance of Electronic Word-of-Mouth (eWOM) of Consumers in Viet Nam

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Abstract: The study is conducted to test the informational influences in the context of information overload on the acceptance of online reviews (a kind of eWOM) in Viet Nam – a case study in Ho Chi Minh city. Using adjustment techniques, inspecting the scales and a theoretical model represent the relationship among the influential factors. The research is based on a sample of 502 consumers who use the Internet to search for online reviews before buying and use Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to test the relationships among the variables. The study results show that the scales of the variables: Message Quality, Source Credibility, Perceived Message Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Message Acceptance attain the validity and reliability in the research. The results also show Perceived Message Usefulness, Message Acceptance are directly and indirectly affected by Message Quality, Source Credibility, and Perceived Ease of Use.

Keywords: *Message Quality, Information Overload, Perceived Message Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Message Acceptance*

JEL Class: C12, M30, M31, M37

I. Introduction

The research works related to eWOM show that eWOM plays an important role in the buying decisions of consumers (Duhan, D. Johnson, S. Wilcox, 1997; Li and Zhan, 2011; Fan et al., 2013). However, when there are many online reviews the consumers might perceive information overload effect – as the volume of the information supply exceeds the limited human information processing capacity (Bawden, Holtham and Courtney, 1999; Luo et al., 2013). As consumers face the situation of information overload they might feel hard to process the information at hand and in some cases, this will reduce the perceived usefulness of the online reviews so that the consumers might have a poor purchase decision.

Previous studies show the importance of information overload and point out many factors have impact significantly on the perception of consumers related to information overload, but rarely studies focus on exploring this issue in the acceptance eWOM information problem (Heylighen, 2002; Cheung et al., 2009; Jackson and Farzaneh, 2012). Therefore, this study is carried out to examine “*The Acceptance of electronic Word-of-Mouth (eWOM) of consumers in the context of Information Overload*” to verify the hypothesis.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 1 introduces research issues; Section 2 presents the literature review; Section 3 presents the proposed model; Section 4 presents research data and methods; Section 5 presents the results of empirical research; the final section summarizes the findings and implications.

II. Literature Review

II.1. Social Communication Theory

According to the theory of Social Communication Theory (Hovland, 1948), communication is the process in which the sender (Communicator) transmits messages (Stimuli) in order to change the behavior of the message recipient (Communicatee), the result of the change is called responsiveness (Response). The Social Communication Theory shows that the process of social communication consists of the interaction of four elements: Communicator, Stimuli, Communicatee, and Response.

The theory is used to investigate the cause of accepting eWOM information from consumers and is used in this study as a reference framework.

II.2. Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

Theory of Reasoned Action – TRA and Theory of Planned Behavior – TPB proposed by Fishbein and Ajzen (1980) to study the relationship between belief, attitude, intention, and behavior.

These two theories prove that a behavior can be predicted or explained by the intention to perform that behavior. Intents are assumed to include motivational factors that influence behavior and are defined as the degree of effort the individual attempts to perform the behavior.

The most important point of these theories for the problem of the acceptance eWOM information is belief factors – the result of the influence of background factors. Researchers on the subject of Information Acceptance are based on this and the Social Communication Theory to interpret and build their research models, such as Davis (1986); Sussman and Siegal (2003); Shen, Cheung and Lee (2013); Arumugam and Omar (2015); Erkan and Evans (2016); Hussain *et al.* (2017); Wang (2018).

II.3. Technology Acceptance Model - TAM

Proposed by Davis (1986), this model was developed based on the Reasonable Action Model – TRA (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1980), adding a number factors – including the Perceived Usefulness factor and the Perceived Ease of Use factor.

In the context of Information Overload, besides the Usefulness of the information, the consumers also interest in the Ease of Use perspective of information. Therefore, the TAM model can be used to explain more the acceptance of eWOM information.

II.4. Information Adoption Model - IAM

As proposed by Sussman & Siegal (2003), the authors argued that acceptance is, in fact, explained by the Technology Acceptance Model – TAM (Davis, 1986) (i.e., based on the Reasoning Action Theory – TPB (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1980) are incomplete as they focus on information systems and on the use of personal computers. It is not possible to explain the process of accepting information. The Information Adoption Model – IAM (Sussman and Siegal, 2003) is the result of combining the TAM model and the Elaboration Likelihood Model – ELM (Petty and Cacioppo, 1986).

II.5. Information Overload

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III. Proposed Model

III.1. Informational Influences

The current research model based on the IAM model of Sussman and Siegal (2003) to assess the effect of informational factors on the acceptance of eWOM information. By this model, the quality of message (Argument quality) is assigned to the central flow and Source credibility is assigned to the peripheral flow, and construct Usefulness is considered as a mediator variable. Therefore, the proposed model (Figure 1) has 3 research hypotheses as follows:

H1: Message Quality has a positive impact on Perceived Message Usefulness (H1+)

H2: Source Credibility has a positive impact on Perceived Message Usefulness (H2+)

H3: Perceived Message Usefulness has a positive impact on Message Acceptance (H3+)

III.2. The Acceptance of eWOM information in the context of Information Overload

When consumers perceive information overload, they tend to oversight information that might support their purchase decisions. Based on the theory of information overload and model TAM (Davis, 1986), the current research model proposes an expanding approach of the IAM model to assess the effect of informational factors and the adding one factor which may affect eWOM consumers' perception of information overload: perceived ease of use. This construct can be regarded as the perception of consumers about the simplicity or complexity of information which they need to process in the context of information overload, we predict this construct will directly and interactively affect the acceptance of eWOM information. The research framework is shown in Figure 1.

In the proposed model, the perceived ease of use construct is measured using the scale of Venkatesh and Bala (2008). Based on the theoretical foundations, the authors propose 2 research hypotheses as follows:

H4: Perceived Ease of Use has a positive impact on Perceived Usefulness (H4+)

H5: Perceived Ease of Use has a positive impact on Message Acceptance (H5+)

III.3. Proposed Model

Figure 1: Model Message Acceptance in the context of Information Overload

Source: The results from the qualitative analysis of researchers (2019)

IV. Research Data and Methods

IV.1. Research data

The participants in the survey are consumers who use the Internet to search for product reviews before actually buying in Viet Nam. Using Message Quality, Source Credibility and Message Acceptance scales of Chou, Wang and Tang (2015), Perceived Usefulness scale of Cheung, Lee, and Rabjohn (2008), Perceived Ease of Use of Venkatesh and Bala (2008).

IV.2. Research Methodology

The quantitative analysis using software IBM SPSS version 22 and IBM SPSS AMOS version 20. The analysis is the following steps: Testing the scale using Cronbach’s Alpha reliability testing and Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA); Testing the measurement model using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) and testing the theoretical model using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) based on the collected data.

V. Research Results

V.1. Representative Sample

Samples were selected according to a convenient sampling method. Data is collected via an online survey for 8 weeks. The result obtained 502 questionnaires answered satisfactorily. The collected data is processed and the statistical description is as follows (Table 1):

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Demographic Feature		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	276	55.0
	Female	216	43.0
	Unknown	10	2.0
Age	18-23	304	60.6
	24-35	198	39.4

Source: Result from the data process of researchers (2019)

V.2. Pre-Test of the questionnaires

V.2.1. Cronbach’s Alpha Results

Research use the scales of Chou, Wang and Tang (2015) for 3 constructs Message Quality (including 3 observable variables, encoded from CHATLUONG1 to CHATLUONG3), Source Credibility (including 3 observable variables, encoded from DOTINCAY1 to DOTINCAY3) and Message Acceptance (including 4 observable variables, encoded from CHAPNHANEWOM1 to CHAPNHANEWOM4); the scale of Cheung, Lee and Rabjohn (2008) for construct Perceived Usefulness (including 3 observable variables, encoded from CN_HUUDUNG1 to CN_HUUDUNG3); and the scale of Venkatesh and Bala (2008) for construct Perceived Ease of Use (including 3 observable variables, encoded from CN_DESUDUNG1 to CN_DESUDUNG3)

The results of the pre-test the questionnaires show that constructs Message Quality, Source Credibility, Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use and Message Acceptance (excluded the observable variable CHAPNHANEWOM3 of substandard quality is rejected) have Cronbach’s Alpha between 0.60 to 0.95 and the Corrected item-total Correlation greater than 0.3 (Table 2), so all attained the reliability and are used for EFA analysis.

Table 2: Summarizes the results of Cronbach’s Alpha testing

Scales	Cronbach’s Alpha	The minimum of Corrected item-total Correlation
Message Quality	0.827	0.656
Source Credibility	0.909	0.763
Perceived Usefulness	0.937	0.862
Perceived Ease of Use	0.940	0.855
Message Acceptance	0.858	0.709

Source: Results from the data process of researchers (2019)

EFA analysis results

The EFA analysis results show that 4 factors are extracted explaining 76.845% (>50%) of the variance with eigenvalue at 1.864, so all observable variables used in the CFA analysis.

CFA analysis results

The CFA analysis results show that chi- square is 181.392 with df = 80, p = 0.000. Cmin / df = 2.267 < 5, meet the requirement for compatibility. TLI = 0.976 > 0.9, CFI = 0.981 > 0.9, GFI = 0.955 > 0.9 and RMSEA = 0.050 < 0.08 are all suitable.

CFA model (Figure 2):

Figure 2. CFA model

Source: Results from the data process of researchers (2019)

Other indexes:

- (1) *Convergent validity:* the CFA results show that the AVE coefficients (Average Variance Extracted) of all constructs are > 0.5 so the scale attain convergent validity.

- (2) *Discriminant validity*: the CFA results show that the square root of AVE greater than correlation coefficients of all constructs, so all constructs attain discriminant validity.
- (3) *Unidimensionality*: the CFA results show that the unidimensionality is attained because all observable variables have factor loading greater than 0.6.
- (4) *Reliability*: Reliability test results through the following indexes: (i) composite reliability, (ii) total variance extracted and (iii) Cronbach’s Alpha testing. The CFA results show that all the scales have composite reliability > 0.5, total variance extracted > 0.5, Cronbach’s Alpha > 0.5, so the scales attain reliability.

Summarized the results of scales testing (Table 3):

Table 3: Summarized the results of scales testing

Scales	No. of items	Reliability Statistics		Variance Extracted	Validity
		Cronbach’s Alpha	Composite		
Message Quality	3	0.827	0.829	0.617	Accepted
Source Credibility	3	0.909	0.912	0.776	
Perceived Usefulness	3	0.937	0.937	0.832	
Perceived Ease of Use	3	0.940	0.941	0.841	
Message Acceptance	3	0.858	0.853	0.661	

Source: results from the data process of researchers (2019)

V.3. Testing the theoretical model

Using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to test the impact of Perceived Senders’ Identity, Message Quality, Source Credibility on Message Acceptance in Viet Nam. The results in Table 4 and Figure 3 as follows:

Table 4: The results of testing the causal relations among constructs (Standardized)

Hypothesis	Causal relations	Estimation	P-value	Conclusion
H1	CN_HUUDUNG <--- CHATLUONG	0.199	*** ¹	Accepted
H2	CN_HUUDUNG <--- DOTINCAY	0.109	***	Accepted
H3	CHAPNHANEWOM <--- CN_HUUDUNG	0.622	***	Accepted
H4	CN_HUUDUNG <--- CN_DESUDUNG	0.222	***	Accepted
H5	CHAPNHANEWOM <--- CN_DESUDUNG	0.286	***	Accepted

Source: Results of the data process by researchers (2019)

The SEM analysis results show that causal relations are statistically significant. Thus, all hypotheses are accepted. The causal relation of all constructs has a positive correlation (estimation correlation coefficients > 0). Furthermore, the SEM analysis results also show that R square of 0.548 is greater than a similar study of Cheung, Lee and Rabjohn (2008) with R square of 0.460, indicating that the proposed model explained more variance of the Message Acceptance construct than the model of Cheung, Lee, and Rabjohn (2008) by adding the construct of Perceived Ease of Use to the IAM model (Sussman and Siegal, 2003).

¹ p-value < 0.05

SEM result model for the standardized model:

Figure 3. SEM results for the standardized model

Source: Results from the data process of researchers (2019)

VI. Discussion and Implications

VI.1. Discussion

“Perceived Ease of Use” (CN_DESUDUNG) has a direct impact on the “Acceptance Message” (CHAPNHANEWOM) with $\beta = 0.286$, which proves that Acceptance Message influenced by the Perceived Ease of Use information in the context of information overload. In other words, perceived ease of use has an impact on increasing the acceptance message, suggesting that consumers appreciate aggregation information rather than full-text information when suffering too much information. This is also a new feature of this research compared to extant studies. Next is the construct “Message Quality” (CHATLUONG) has a relatively influence on the “Perceived Usefulness” (CN_HUUDUNG) with $\beta = 0.199$, which proves that perceived usefulness is quite affected by the message quality; in the same manner the construct “Source Credibility” (DOTINCAY) has an influence on the “Perceived Usefulness”(CN_HUUDUNG) with $\beta = 0.109$. That’s mean message quality and source credibility has a quite impact on increasing the perceived usefulness, through which increasing message acceptance; shows that consumers are also interested in the quality aspect of the message and the credibility of message sources, which is consistent with similar studies, such as those of Shen et al. (2013), Tseng & Wang (2016).

Besides, the regression coefficient of message quality (CHATLUONG) indirectly impact on message acceptance (CHAPNHANEWOM): $message\ quality \times\ perceived\ usefulness = 0.124^2$. This shows that when other factors do not change, message quality increases 1, message acceptance increases 0.124. The regression coefficient of perceived ease of use (CN_DESUDUNG) indirectly impact on message acceptance (CHAPNHANEWOM): $perceived\ ease\ of\ use \times\ perceived\ usefulness = 0.138^3$. This shows that when other factors do not change, the perceived ease of use increases 1, message acceptance decreases 0.138. Similarly, the source credibility increase 1, message acceptance increases 0.068⁴.

SEM results show that message quality, source credibility has a positive impact on perceived usefulness, so the hypotheses H1, H2 are accepted; perceived usefulness has a positive impact on message acceptance, so hypothesis H3 are accepted; perceived ease of use has a positive impact on perceived usefulness, so hypothesis H4 is accepted; perceived ease of use has a positive impact on message acceptance, so hypothesis H5 are accepted;

In conclusion, the research results are consistent with results of previous studies in the impact of message quality, source credibility on message acceptance through mediator perceived usefulness such as Cheung, Lee, and Rabjohn (2008), Shen, Cheung and Lee (2013), Tseng and Wang (2016); message quality and source credibility increase the ability to accept eWOM information of consumers. Furthermore, the addition of Perceived Ease of Use (CN_DESUDUNG) construct to IAM model of Sussman and Siegal (2003) - to reflect the acceptance of eWOM information in the context of information overload - shows that this situation has a significant statistics, thereby explaining more the variation of message acceptance comparing to previous studies.

² 0.199x0.622

³ 0.222x0.622

⁴ 0.109x0.622

VI.2. Implications

This study helps businesses understand the important factors that influence the acceptance of eWOM information, which are informational factors (Message Quality and Source Credibility), a factor related to the information overload (Perceived Ease of Use). The informational factors indirectly impact on the acceptance of eWOM information through mediators Perceived Usefulness. The ease of use factor, directly and indirectly, impact on the acceptance of eWOM information through mediators Perceived Usefulness.

When consumers accept eWOM information, they might be able to use this kind of information as a basis for their buying decisions. Therefore, businesses might be able to develop eWOM communication as an effective marketing tool in the form of allowing consumers submitting their voice about products, services; send comments; write reviews ... on the company's website. Furthermore, businesses might associate with other independent websites specializing in review products, services to invite them trying products, services. This gives consumers a chance to have products' information objectively from various sources before making a purchase decision. Besides, businesses might also link their websites with some social websites, so that businesses can collect consumers' feedback on these websites.

The most important thing businesses should know that is if there is too much eWOM information the consumers might suffer information overload and tend to use the information provided in the format of the aggregation rather than full-text information.

The experience gained during the research is the basis for the completion of research activities on the impact of eWOM information on the acceptance eWOM information and accordingly the intention of consumers to purchase decisions in future studies.

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